

Evaluation Of the Fuel Value Indices of Selected Wood Fuel Species Used in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study evaluates the fuel value indices of selected wood fuel species in Nigeria, focusing on the hardwood *Iroko* (*Milicia excelsa*) and softwood *Obeche* (*Triplochiton scleroxylon*). Proximate and ultimate analyses were conducted on 2kg samples of sawdust (Biomass) from each species to determine their moisture content, ash content, and calorific value, bulk density, the percentage quantity of composition of Carbon (C), Oxygen (O), Hydrogen (H), Nitrogen (N) and Sulphur (S) respectively. The threshold values for high fuel indices were set as follows: calorific value ≥ 19.5 kg/m², ash content $< 1.5\%$, moisture content $< 25\%$, bulk density ≥ 320 kg/m³, carbon content $\leq 48\%$, sulfur $\leq 0.15\%$, nitrogen $\leq 0.8\%$, hydrogen $\geq 6.0\%$, and oxygen $\leq 40\%$. The proximate analysis showed that the calorific values of *Milicia excelsa* and *Triplochiton scleroxylon* were 94.9 and 10.9 kg/m², Ash content was 3.3% and 6.1%, with moisture contents of 6.0% and 6.7%, respectively. Bulk densities were 17.8 and 16.2 kg/m³. The ultimate analysis revealed their carbon content of 33.2% and 29.6%, sulfur content of 0.08% and 0.12%, nitrogen content of 0.57% and 0.65%, hydrogen content of 3.1% and 2.78%, and oxygen content of 24.1% and 22.7%, respectively. These results indicate that both hardwood and softwood species possess favorable fuel indices, suggesting they can contribute to a cleaner environment if used sustainably. The study helps enhance understanding of the suitability and efficiency of different wood fuel species in Nigeria, providing insights for better fuelwood management and utilization strategies. The research recommends using this methodology to study more wood biomass species.

Keywords; Biomass; Wood fuel; Climate change; Fuel indices;

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INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is rich in both renewable and non-renewable energy sources, such as hydroelectric power and natural gas. However, the government's current reliance on fossil fuels (like petroleum and gas) for electricity generation may not suffice to meet the growing energy needs of the population. Additionally, the environmental impact of fossil fuels has become a major concern in today's energy discussions. Unlike renewable sources, fossil fuels are non-recyclable and release harmful

byproducts, such as carbon (IV) oxide, without reabsorption. Issues like oil spills and severe air pollution further worsen the situation, both in reality and in theory.

Given the rising demand for electricity and cleaner energy, researchers have increasingly turned their attention to alternative energy sources, including wood waste (biomass) (Kanekezi and Kthyon, 2006). Biomass consists of organic, biodegradable materials derived from plants, animals, and microorganisms, including agricultural, forestry, and municipal waste Ogunsola *et al.*, (2018). Among these, wood biomass stands out as a key renewable energy source in developing nations, playing a vital role in rural energy supply. A significant portion of this potential comes from wood processing byproducts, particularly wood shavings.

The growing significance of wood as a fuel source has spurred research into optimizing wood selection and combustion processes to maximize energy output (Zelinka *et al.*, 2022). Key wood properties such as moisture content, calorific value, ash content, density, and specific gravity have been empirically studied to determine which species perform best as fuels Glass and Zelinka, (2021). Additionally, metrics like fuel value index (FVI) and combustion efficiency, derived through numerical calculations, help rank wood species based on their suitability Evbuomwan and Okorji, (2018). The FVI accounts for multiple factors, weighing both positive and negative attributes.

Several characteristics influence the choice of wood for fuel, including flame type and duration, coal formation, smoke emission, ignition ease, flavor imparted to food, and ash residue. Researchers commonly use statistical tools such as Pearson's correlation coefficient, Spearman's rank correlation, and one-way ANOVA to analyze relationships between these properties. These analyses, conducted manually or with application software like SPSS, have proven highly effective even for byproducts like sawdust.

Wood fuel is abundant and locally accessible, providing a reliable energy source when harvested sustainably. It originates from diverse sources, including forests, woodlands, processing byproducts, recycled wood, and processed biofuels. Communities across socio-economic levels often revert to wood energy during economic crises, natural disasters, conflicts, or fossil fuel shortages.

Wood is categorized by density into hardwood (0.6–1.2 g/cm³) and softwood (0.3–0.6 g/cm³) Lengowski *et al.*, (2020). Evaluating FVI is essential for determining biofuel efficiency, as it reflects the bioenergy potential of different species. Studies indicate that some woods exhibit higher FVIs due to their chemical and physical properties. This study therefore assesses two commonly used wood fuel species in Nigerian communities, analyzing their FVIs based on fundamental properties.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Source and Classification of Wood Samples

The hardwood (Iroko, *Milicia excelsa*) and softwood (Obeche, *Triplochiton scleroxylon*) used in this study were sourced from the plank market (Iso Pako) in Bodija Market, Ibadan. These species were selected based on their density classifications, with softwoods defined as having a density of 0.3–0.6 g/cm³ and hardwoods ≥ 1.2 g/cm³. Wood density and specific gravity indicate the amount of solid wood material per unit volume. The standard method for determining density involves calculating the ratio of dry wood weight to its green volume, known as basic density Tsoumis, (1991). While density can be expressed in various units (g/cm³, kg/m³, or lb/ft³), specific gravity

is dimensionless (e.g., 0.45 rather than 0.45 g/ml) since it compares wood density to water (1 g = 1 mL). It is important to note that density values may vary significantly depending on whether measurements are based on dry weight/dry volume, green weight/green volume, or other methods.

Sample Preparation and Analysis

From each wood type, 2 kg of sun-dried shavings (sawdust) were produced. The hardwood (Iroko) sawdust was labeled Sample A, while the softwood (Obeche) sawdust was labeled Sample B. These samples were then subjected to proximate and ultimate analyses at the Multipurpose Laboratory of the Federal College of Animal Health and Production Technology, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Proximate Analysis

The proximate analysis evaluated the (i) moisture Content (%) which affects combustion efficiency lower moisture (<20%) improves ignition and heat output. (ii) Ash Content (%) Indicates inorganic residue; high ash (>5%) reduces fuel quality by causing boiler clogging and heat loss. Lower values of Moisture and Ash improve combustion (iii) Calorific Value (MJ/kg) measures energy content the higher values imply enhancement of Fuel Value Index (FVI). (hardwoods: 18–22 MJ/kg; softwoods: 16–20 MJ/kg) enhance Fuel Value Index (FVI). And (iv) Bulk Density (kg/m³) that determines the fuel compactness the denser fuels burn longer and are more energy-efficient for storage/transport. Higher values of both Calorific Value and Bulk Density increase energy output and practicality these are the key parameters in assessing biomass fuel quality (Vasileiadou, 2021). These properties influence the Fuel Value Index (FVI)

Ultimate Analysis

The ultimate analysis determined the elemental composition of Carbon (C), Hydrogen (H), Oxygen (O), Nitrogen (N), and Sulfur (S) of the biomass, which indirectly impacts fuel quality (Baqir et al., 2019; Racero-Galaraga et al., 2024). Although not part of the standard FVI formula, but elemental composition influences combustion behavior: The FVI integrates these properties to rank biomass fuel efficiency as shown in equation (1) (Sadiku et al., 2016; Islam et al., 2019).

$$FVI = \frac{\text{Calorific Value} \times \text{Bulk Density}}{\text{Moisture Content} \times \text{Ash Content}} \quad (1)$$

Analytical Methodology

Proximate and ultimate analyses were performed on 2 kg sawdust samples from each wood species to evaluate key fuel properties. The proximate analysis determined moisture content, ash content, calorific value, and bulk density, while the ultimate analysis quantified the elemental composition (Carbon [C], Oxygen [O], Hydrogen [H], Nitrogen [N], and Sulfur [S]). Although elemental composition is not directly included in standard Fuel Value Index (FVI) calculations, it provides critical insights into why certain fuels perform better (Leach *et al.*, 2022). For comprehensive fuel characterization, FVI should be combined with proximate (moisture, ash, volatiles) and ultimate (C, H, O, N, S) analyses, as elemental composition indirectly affects combustion efficiency, emissions, and energy output (Baqir et al., 2019; Racero-Galaraga et al., 2024). For this study, the threshold values for optimal fuel performance were set as: Calorific value ≥ 19.5 MJ/kg content $< 1.5\%$ Moisture content $< 25\%$ Bulk density ≥ 320 kg/m³ Carbon $\leq 48\%$, Sulfur $\leq 0.15\%$, Nitrogen $\leq 0.8\%$ Hydrogen $\geq 6.0\%$, Oxygen $\leq 40\%$

Analytical Methods

Moisture content

%Moisture was Calculated using equation (2-4)

$$\%DM = \frac{w_3 - w_0}{w_1 - w_0} \times 100 \% \quad (2)$$

$$\%Moisture = \frac{w_3 - w_0}{w_1 - w_0} \times 100 \% \quad (3)$$

Therefore

$$\%Moisture = 100 - DM \quad (4)$$

Where

w_0 = weight of empty crucible w_1 = weight of empty crucible + sample

w_3 = weight of empty crucible + oven dried sample DM=dried sample

Ash Content

$$Ash\ Content = \frac{weight\ of\ oven\ dried\ Ash}{initial\ weight\ of\ Ash} \times 100\% \quad (5)$$

Calorific Value was measured by comparing sample temperature rise to benzoic acid. Bulk density was Derived from oven-dried weight divided by original volume

Ultimate Analysis:

Carbon & Hydrogen: were quantified using CO₂ and H₂O absorption (Eqn. 6–7).

$$\%Carbon = \frac{a \times 0.2727}{weight\ of\ sample} \times 100\% \quad (6)$$

$$\%Hydrogen = \frac{b \times 0.1117}{weight\ of\ sample} \times 100\% \quad (7)$$

Where a and b are Where a and b are quantity of CO₂ and H₂O respectively

Nitrogen was Analyzed via the Micro-Kjeldahl method (Ates and Kaya, 2021).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings will be presented in this section, comparing the fuel properties of Iroko and Obeche sawdust based on the above analyses. Figures 1 and 2 represents the plot of the analysis of the proximate and ultimate respectively. The proximate analysis showed that the calorific values of *Milicia excelsa* and *Triplochiton scleroxylon* were 94.9 and 10.9 kg/m², Ash content was 3.3% and 6.1%, with moisture contents of 6.0% and 6.7%, respectively. Bulk densities were 17.8 and 16.2 kg/m³. The ultimate analysis revealed their carbon content of 33.2% and 29.6%, sulfur content of 0.08% and 0.12%, nitrogen content of 0.57% and 0.65%, hydrogen content of 3.1% and 2.78%, and oxygen content of 24.1% and 22.7%, respectively. These results indicate that both hardwood and softwood species possess favorable fuel indices, suggesting they can contribute to a cleaner environment if used sustainably.

Fig. 1 The bar chat of the Proximate Analysis.

Fig.2 The bar chat of the ultimate analysis

CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluates the fuel value indices (FVI) of selected wood fuel species in Nigeria, focusing on the hardwood *Iroko* (*Milicia excelsa*) and softwood *Obeche* (*Triplochiton scleroxylon*). Proximate and ultimate analyses were conducted on 2kg samples of sawdust (Biomass) from each species to determine their moisture content, ash content, and calorific value, bulk density, the percentage quantity of composition of Carbon (C), Oxygen (O), Hydrogen (H), Nitrogen (N) and Sulphur (S) respectively. These results indicate that both hardwood and softwood species possess favorable fuel indices, suggesting they can contribute to a cleaner environment if used sustainably. The study helps enhance understanding of the suitability and efficiency of different wood fuel species in Nigeria, providing insights for better fuelwood management and utilization strategies. The research recommends using this methodology to study more wood biomass species.

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